

Can X (Twitter) be used to Predict Tourism Patterns? Yes!

Raidah Hanifah^{*1,2}, Nicholas Malleson^{†1}, Victoria Houlden^{‡1}
and Alexis Comber^{§1}

¹School of Geography, University of Leeds

²Departement of Informatics, Institut Teknologi Sumatera

GISRUK 2024

Summary

This study evaluates and compares X (Twitter) as an alternative data source to standard tourism data. The study focuses on Bali, in Indonesia as Indonesia ranks 6th globally in active X users. The results indicate a strong correlation (0.89) between X data and official government sources on domestic tourist numbers. Despite potential challenges like multiple arrivals and extended stays, the findings indicate the usefulness of incorporating social media data within formal analyses of tourist flows and suggest exploration of other platforms for a more comprehensive study.

KEYWORDS: Tourism Data, Domestic Tourist, Social Media, Twitter, X.

1. Introduction

Bali is a popular Indonesian tourist destination, boasts stunning tropical beaches, unique Hindu-influenced culture, and vibrant traditions. Temples, ceremonies, and artistic performances enrich Bali's cultural landscape. Notably, the island's allure extends to both domestic and international tourists. In 2019, Bali welcomed a peak of 10.5 million domestic visitors (Tourism Office, 2020), but the COVID-19 pandemic caused a 56% decline in 2020 (Tourism Office, 2021). Despite this, domestic tourism plays a vital role in sustaining Bali's industry, with millions still visiting amid the global challenges. Figure 1 depicts the geographic location of Bali within Indonesia and its proximity to neighbouring countries.

Figure 1 Bali's location within Indonesia and neighbouring countries.

* gyrh@leeds.ac.uk/raidah.hanifah@if.itera.ac.id

† n.s.malleson@leeds.ac.uk

‡ v.houlden@leeds.ac.uk

§ a.comber@leeds.ac.uk

The Indonesian government's official statistical organisation, Badan Pusat Statistik (BPS), collaborates with the Ministry of Tourism to track tourist numbers. Traditionally, domestic tourist figures were obtained through direct interviews with a sample of 50,000 households (Arifatin & Ruslani, 2020). However, BPS states this method had limitations, providing only provincial-level estimates, and relying on participants' memories. Since 2020, BPS transitioned to a digital survey, employing a web-based questionnaire. Additionally, they introduced Big Data technology, utilizing Mobile Phone Data (MPD) from cellular operators to enhance accuracy, detail, speed, and efficiency (Arifatin & Utari, 2021). Despite its advantages, the use of MPD faces challenges like the need for operator collaboration and privacy concerns for their customers (Ahas et al., 2010).

This study aims to investigate alternative data sources, specifically social media X, formerly known as Twitter, and their potential as complementary resources to tourism data in Indonesia, with a focus on Bali. Indonesia ranks 6th in the globe with no fewer than 14.8 million active X users (Kemp 2023) indicating around 5% of Indonesia's total population. The substantial number of users is anticipated to have a positive impact on the availability of a large amount of data. The study innovatively compares social media data with government-provided information, leveraging X's extensive user base to gain unique insights into digital behaviors. This approach bridges the gap between social media dynamics and official government statistics, offering a better understanding of synergies and disparities in these datasets.

2. Methodology

2.1. Data Collection

Two primary datasets are utilised for this study, covering the period from 2019 to 2021. The initial dataset is sourced from the social media platform X and obtained through the Twitter Academic API in the year 2022. The retrieved tweets were extracted from the Bali region within bounding box coordinates of 115.066818, -8.853321; 115.347931, -8.586181. The dataset includes the username, user ID, tweets in text format, date when tweets posted, and geolocation where the tweets posted (if activated/provided by user). The second dataset was sourced from the official report on tourism in Bali, obtained by downloading the "Bali Tourism Statistics Book for 2019 to 2021" from the official government website (Tourism Office, 2020, 2021, 2022). The report provides a detailed breakdown of tourist numbers, nationalities, and entrance ports, with monthly recordings.

2.2. Domestic Tourist Detection

Domestic tourists were defined as individuals who come from Indonesia but are not residents of Bali province. Identifying domestic tourists from X data was undertaken through a four-stage process. The initial phase was to identify the individual users in the dataset and gather their profile information, including their origin country, from X. The second phase involved geocoding the user's origin country location using 'geocode_osm' function in R (Kolb, 2019). However, some locations cannot be geocoded because they contain several locations in the text. Therefore, the third stage employed the word frequency approach to retrieve the first locations that appear in the text. The last phase classified the tourists according to their geocoded origin country. X users identified as coming from Indonesia, except those from Bali, were retained for analysis.

2.3. Temporal Analysis

This study analysed temporal trend of domestic tourist arrivals by determining the number of domestic tourists visiting Bali each month based. Each tourist counts as only one arrival each month. The results were then compared to official data, and the correlation was assessed using several methods, including monthly ratio trend, Pearson correlation coefficient (Anon, 2008), and linear regression model (Bingham & Fry, 2010).

3. Outcomes and Discussion

3.1. Domestic Tourist Number Comparison

A total of 2,164,237 tweets were gathered, coming from 64,614 distinct users. After following the

approach outlined above, it was determined that 15,450 users were domestic visitors. Figure 2 shows the monthly distribution of tourists, determined by aggregating the number of tweets from individual users and normalising the values. Each user is considered as a single arrival per month, regardless of the number of tweets they post in the same month. The two time-series data were normalised to a scale of 0-1000 using the min-max approach (Shalabi, Shaaban & Kasasbeh, 2006).

Figure 2 The trend of domestic tourist arrivals (normalised values) for a 36-month period (January 2019 - December 2021)

3.2. Result Evaluation

Figure 3 Monthly ratio of official data to X data (raw values) for domestic tourist arrivals.

Several methodologies were employed to assess the correlation between predicted tourist numbers derived from X and raw official statistics. Figure 3 illustrates the trend in monthly ratios between X and official data. In 2019, the ratio remained generally stable, with an exception in June, coinciding with a notable peak in domestic tourist arrivals. However, the number of tweets in June did not proportionately increase, resulting in an outlier ratio for that month. Subsequently, in 2020, the ratio exhibited a significant decline from April to June, indicating a sharper decrease in official data compared to X data. This aligns with the period when the Indonesian government implemented

nationwide movement restrictions in response to the escalating spread of COVID-19 (Permatasari, 2021). The trend later experienced a rebound and fluctuations throughout the remainder of the year. In 2021, official data gradually surpassed X data every six months.

The Pearson correlation test was employed to compare the monthly counts from X and official tourism data resulting in a correlation of 0.89 data. This indicates that the two data sources have a strong positive linear correlation. A linear regression model was used to determine whether X and official data are linearly related. The outcome of regression model between the official data as the dependent variable and the X data is depicted in Table 1. X (Twitter) is a significant predictor of official count data and the model accounts for 79.49% of the variability in official data. This indicates that the model can be used to predict the number of domestic tourist arrivals.

Table 1. Linear regression model summary for official and X (Twitter) data (raw values) of domestic tourist arrivals with R squared = 0.7949.

Term	Estimate	Std Error	Statistic	P-value
(Intercept)	-143022.	63944.	-2.24	0.0032
X (Twitter)	819.	71.3	11.5	<0.0000

4. Conclusion and Further Work

The research findings reveal a strong correlation between the data on domestic tourist numbers estimated from X and the data acquired from official government sources. This result is demonstrated by the Pearson correlation test, with a coefficient value of 0.89, and the linear regression model indicated X data to be a significant predictor of official tourism data. Future work will investigate international tourist patterns, the activities of tourists from their tweets, and how different activities vary spatially and by activity for different tourist groups. Some challenges remain, including the potential for multiple arrivals within a single month or tourists who extend their stay beyond one month. This investigation is necessary to comprehend the basic factor responsible for significant fluctuations in the monthly ratio trend. Furthermore, exploring alternative social media platforms is recommended to enhance study outcomes and address the discontinuation of the free Twitter API.

5. Acknowledgements

This study is supported by the Indonesian Endowment Fund for Education/Lembaga Pengelola Dana Pendidikan (LPDP) and University of Leeds.

References

- Ahas, R., Silm, S., Järv, O., Saluveer, E. & Tiru, M. (2010) Using Mobile Positioning Data to Model Locations Meaningful to Users of Mobile Phones. *Journal of Urban Technology*. 17 (1), 3–27. doi:10.1080/10630731003597306.
- Arifatin, D. & Ruslani, A. (2020) *Domestic Tourism Statistics 2019*. BPS-Statistics Indonesia.
- Arifatin, D. & Utari, R. (2021) *Domestic Tourism Statistics 2020*. BPS-Statistics Indonesia.
- Bingham, N.H. & Fry, J.M. (2010) *Regression*. Springer Undergraduate Mathematics Series. London, Springer London. doi:10.1007/978-1-84882-969-5.
- W. Kirch (ed.) (2008) Pearson’s Correlation Coefficient. In: *Encyclopedia of Public Health*. Dordrecht, Springer Netherlands. pp. 1090–1091. doi:10.1007/978-1-4020-5614-7_2569.
- Kolb, J.-P. (2019) Using Web Services to Work with Geodata in R. *The R Journal*. 11 (2), 6. doi:10.32614/RJ-2019-041.
- Permatasari, D. (2021) *Covid-19 Policy from PSBB to PPKM Four Levels*. 31 July 2021.

<https://kompaspedia.kompas.id/baca/infografik/kronologi/kebijakan-covid-19-dari-psbb-hingga-ppkm-empat-level>.

Shalabi, L.A., Shaaban, Z. & Kasasbeh, B. (2006) Data Mining: A Preprocessing Engine. *Journal of Computer Science*. 2 (9), 735–739. doi:10.3844/jcssp.2006.735.739.

Tourism Office, B.G. (2020) *Bali Tourism Statistics Book 2019*. 2020. <https://disparda.baliprov.go.id/buku-statistik-pariwisata-bali-tahun-2019/> [Accessed: 12 August 2023].

Tourism Office, B.G. (2021) *Bali Tourism Statistics Book 2020*. 2021. <https://disparda.baliprov.go.id/buku-statistik-pariwisata-bali-2020/>.

Tourism Office, B.G. (2022) *Bali Tourism Statistics Book 2021*. 2022. <https://disparda.baliprov.go.id/buku-statistik-pariwisata-bali-tahun-2021/2022/05/> [Accessed: 12 August 2023].

Biographies

Raidah Hanifah is a third-year Ph.D. candidate in the School of Geography at the University of Leeds and serves as a lecturer at the Institut Teknologi Sumatera. Her research focuses on data mining, social media analysis, and spatial-temporal analysis.

Alexis Comber is a Professor of Spatial Data Analytics at the University of Leeds. His diverse interests span various application areas, including land cover/land use, demographics, public health, agriculture, bioenergy, and accessibility. Lex employs a multidisciplinary approach from geocomputation, mathematics, statistics, and computer science.

Nicolas Malleon is a Professor of Spatial Science at the University of Leeds. His primary research involves developing spatial computer models of social phenomena, specifically focusing on crime simulation and models of urban areas.

Victoria Houlden is a Lecturer in Urban Data Science at the School of Geography at the University of Leeds. Vikki's expertise encompasses urban science, spatial inequality, greenspace, health, mental well-being, places left behind, and GIS.